

Introduction: Growing back better to regenerate STEM Education

Eamon Costello^a

^aSchool of STEM Education, Innovation and Global Studies, DCU Institute of Education, Dublin City University, Dublin, Ireland

CONTACT Eamon Costello, eamon.costello@dcu.ie

On the 24th and 25th of June 2022 educators, researchers, teachers, students, and other members of the STEM education learning ecosystem from Ireland and beyond gathered in Dublin City University for CASTeL's 9th STEM Education research conference (SMEC). Taking a cue from what has been posited as an affective turn in social science research (Dukes et al, 2022), the conference was convened under the broad thematic banner of “growing back better” in the service of “regenerating STEM education”. This growth alludes to the personal flourishing of students but importantly also their teachers. As we collectively but cautiously emerged from lock-downed learning, we sought to include under the conference call a cognisance of the role of emotion and well-being for education. The verb “grow” was deliberately chosen as an alternative to build. We cannot “build back” brains, bodies or battered spirits - these things must grow. Growth also reminds us that we share this planet with a vast range of other organic beings. As the focus turns towards grave planetary issues, of climate change and ecological collapse, we will need constant reminders as to the ultimate effects of human activities, including those in the domains of education and industry (Facer 2020; MacGilChrist 2021; Selwyn 2021).

Affective models of human behavior focus on emotions, feelings, motivations, moods. The affective construct of belonging came through strongly in the conference such as a predictor of persistence and success in STEM education and research as highlighted by the research of our keynote speaker Associate Professor Mica Estrada in her work on integration in scientific communities. The environmental element was captured by Associate Professor Maria Evagouru in her wide-ranging talk on research into socio-scientific issues through vivid depictions of her students learning in and about the environments of saltwater swamps. Affective education does not supersede behavioral or cognitive models however, rather it only incorporate or builds on them. Fittingly then our opening keynote Professor Mieke De Cock gave a tour de force of her work in the fascinating area of representations in STEM and how students may work with abstractions to build types of representational fluency to better solve mathematical and scientific problems. You can read the abstracts of these talks and many more in these proceedings but we also have a selection of full papers which we next briefly introduce.

The area of problem solving is explored in several of the papers in these proceedings. Fitzsimons and Ní Fhloinn (2022) give an account of a doctoral study that developed a purpose-built mathematics intervention in the form of a classroom programme for highly-able mathematics students in “Transition Year” of the Irish school system. This intervention centered on group work based problem solving. An insightful paper by Neururer and Ni Shuilleabhain (2022) report on timely research investigating post-primary mathematics teachers’ concerns and feedback around problem-solving and associated classroom-based assessment in the context of curriculum change. The paper reports on interview data suggesting that teachers feel constrained in attempting change to traditional practice, lacking both confidence and resources under the added pressure of a packed curriculum. But these teachers also give testimony to a desire to collaborate, develop and deepen their practice with each other. Further issues with teachers and problem-solving pedagogies are highlighted by Owens and Nolan (2022) whose findings from work with a cohort of in-service mathematics post-primary teachers showing how they often fall back on computational skills and previously learned routines and procedures rather than on developing problem solving skills.

Critical junctures representing the transition between educational levels and settings for learners were explored in two papers (Howard, Nic Mhuirí, & O Reilly, 2022; Kaur, McLoughlin & Grimes; 2022). Howard, Nic Mhuirí, and O Reilly (2022), using a methodology of narrative enquiry, report on a study that suggests that participants' mathematical understanding could be deepened by varying the forms of assessment for both formative and summative work. Kaur, McLoughlin & Grimes (2022) give a clear account of ongoing research using Practitioner Inquiry. Findings reported here show much encouragement for this approach and for enabling teachers to develop their practice to better guide students in problem solving.

Given the almost perennial issue of Mathematics teacher shortages, the issue of teacher identity, explored here in the work of Quirke (2022) makes a very useful contribution to our understanding of teachers who teach mathematics “out-of-field”. Representations of identity, comprised of the “self-understandings” or stories, told by teachers about themselves as reported in this research may have implications for mathematics professional education programmes and for informing conversations around teacher certification. The theme of identity for women in STEM careers is explored by Slattery, Prendergast and Ní Ríordáin (2022) whose paper offers insights into encouraging younger girls to feel they belong in STEM fields and to have confidence in essential skills they can bring to bear in associated careers. Lastly, in another of the set of papers focused on Mathematics published here, Howard and Ní Fhloinn (2022) report on lessons learned from providing online mathematics support during lockdown and give insight into which elements could be retained as students increasingly seek digital-first supports.

Although a preponderance of the papers here focused on Mathematics, two final papers deal with the holistic conception of STEM more broadly. A paper by McLoughlin and Chadwick (2022)

outlines an approach adopted to design a Framework for STEAM Education for the Youthreach initiative. This framework was developed via stakeholder perspectives and by drawing on relevant literature. It is to be used in alternative education provision to reach learners who need it most. Lastly, a very insightful and wide-ranging scholarly piece by Mooney Simmie (2022), critically weaves together studies from STEM and wider education literature from a policy perspective. The author makes a compelling case for STEM Education as “a human and relational endeavour, a sociological project that needs to be understood as an open and dynamic system - for assuring human emancipation as well as living well in a vibrant dynamic democracy - rather than a static and predictable system” (Mooney Simmie 2022, p 74). This is a very fitting sentiment on which to conclude this short introductory note from the conference chair and thus make way for the published proceedings proper.

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